

BUILDING INFORMATION MODELING FOR PRECAST CONCRETE COMPONENTS IN DEVELOPED NATIONS

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Abstract

Since the construction sector consumes a significant part of each country's capital and inevitably affects the development of other countries, especially emerging countries, it is necessary to use methods, techniques, and technology in this business. He led the development of several construction projects that produced quality, durable buildings in less time and at a lower cost. BIM building information modeling technology, which, after a few years since its inception, has occupied a significant part of the global construction market, is one of the most useful and important technologies in the world and a revolution in the construction industry. The high sensitivity of the construction and implementation of prefabricated concrete structures on the one hand and the growing need to build fast and cost-effective structures on the other hand, prompted many construction companies around the world to use this technology in the construction of structures. The use of precast concrete is presented in this research in order to investigate the role of building information modeling technology in the creation of precast concrete buildings and also the benefits of using this technology for such structures, using library studies and past research to obtain results.

Keywords: Structures, BIM, Concrete, Technology, Construction

Introduction

Due to the unique implementation challenges and hurdles that the majority of construction projects face, it is vital to employ contemporary technology to address these issues in order to have an influence on the two crucial elements of time and cost. Avoid being impacted by things that have a negative impact on a project's success or failure. Currently, there has been significant advancement in the introduction of numerous ways and procedures. The use of Building Information Modeling (BIM) technology and its integration with the re-engineering process and its incredibly impressive advantages in the process of building and implementing projects, for instance, by numerous engineering organizations, particularly civil, architectural, and facility engineers worldwide, is increasing. Civil engineers have gotten used to it and employ this technology to streamline their projects, particularly prefabricated concrete constructions (1). Prefabricated concrete components are seen in figure 1. (21).

Figure 1: prefabricated concrete parts (21)

In these situations, in addition to the project's direct negative impacts, there may also be indirect negative effects, among which it is possible to note the diminished reputation. In addition to the aforementioned negative consequences for the project, there may also be beneficial benefits, such as when we are compelled to adopt current technology to cope with the changes imposed on the project. As a consequence, we unintentionally influence the building engineering community's introduction of a new technology. This alone might be seen as advantageous. Building information modeling technology is one of the practical and effective innovations that recently joined the nation's construction industry. As a result of the significant transformation and revolution that the introduction of this technology into engineering has brought about in the fields of civil engineering and architecture, it is essential to take concrete steps to improve the nation's building conditions by conducting enough research in this area. (1) Figure 2 shows how a building has been transformed into a digital duplicate by modeling the building data. (20)

Figure 2: Digital replica (20)

Literature Review

Building information modeling has been the subject of several studies, all of which dealt with various facets and applications of the subject. Each study, using a different methodology, has shown the need to investigate the current state, efficacy, and knowledge of the advantages of this technology and has contributed to its advancement, development, and broader use. The evaluated studies are generally grouped into three groups. The first group includes studies that have been done to examine the level of acceptability of building information modeling as well as the barriers to and issues with its implementation. The second area consists of studies that have looked at the uses, advantages, and efficiency of developing information modeling technology; the third category is devoted to studies that have been done to create a model for bettering and understanding technology. (4)

They found obstacles to the implementation of building information modeling in a different research. This study, which gathered the opinions of construction industry experts through a questionnaire, revealed that they are uninterested in and inexperienced in building information modeling. It also revealed that the biggest barriers to its adoption among policymakers are a lack of support and a lack of motivation to promote it. Other barriers to the implementation of this technology in Iran include a lack of awareness and understanding as well as the absence of training materials. Additional barriers to the use of this technology were found to include opposition to altering conventional practices, expenses, the speed of the Internet, a lack of critical infrastructure, and ignorance of possible advantages (5).

However, compared to other nations in the globe, the United States of America is far ahead in the creation of scientific publications in the area of building information modeling, according to research done up to the end of 2015. The Scandinavian nations also have 59 of the papers produced in this branch of science globally. This subject is based on the analysis of the chart created in 2012 by Carneiro et al.

Additional research was conducted till 2015, and the order and rating of the nations are still in place. It should be noted that the stark contrast depicted in the diagram below may be the result of varying operating systems, a greater value placed on new technologies, the presence of educational institutions with a focus on building information modeling and construction management, as well as other factors. (6) The number of publications published in developed nations is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Articles published in the field of building information modeling by countries until 2015

Methodology

I have written this article using library methods and previous research. On the other hand, using articles up to 2015, I reviewed the previous research that shows the impact of BIM on the construction industry. In this article, I have described the effect of precast concrete using beams.

Building information modeling

The creation, use, and management of vital building design and project data via the use of technology, or BIM, allows for the creation of intelligent 3D digital models that can be seen and used throughout the life cycle of a building. (2-3) BIM software is based on 3D parametric modeling, a technique that links pertinent data to digital replicas of real-world building components (such as walls, columns, electrical, and plumbing) to describe their characteristics (3). Geometry, relationship geometric properties (such as parallelism, offset from), material quality, design performance, supplier, timetable, cost, and other details are examples of this information (3). A sophisticated 3D building model is created using BIM platforms, and BIM audit and analysis tools are utilized to investigate or enhance the depth of information in the model (3). You can see in Figure 4 that by using building information modeling, you can view and check all project information before starting.

Figure 4: Building information modeling (22)

Building information modeling advantages

- Time-related issues: Using BIM often cuts down on the amount of time needed to generate construction drawings.
- 4D models: By using 4D tools, the construction planning chain may be evaluated and shared with other members of the project team. The components of the building model should be organized into groups based on the phases of construction and connected to project planning activities.
- Cost-related issues: One of the benefits of BIM is that each component provides data on its length, breadth, and height, as well as any other information required for a quantitative estimate of the project.
- Eliminating waste: The capacity to swiftly build alternative models, keep the information and coherence of the specified model (preventing interference), and generate automated reports all contribute to stable and trustworthy data that is mostly discarded and recreated. reduces the amount of effort and waiting for information.
- Quality: With BIM's many possibilities, it is simple to provide the chance for the quality to be verified and the ultimate objective of higher-quality buildings to be realized. (7)

Building information modeling Disadvantages

- Low adoption of new technologies and traditional working methods in construction projects, particularly in developing nations.
- The requirement for job training for employees and operators in contracting firms, consulting firms, and organizations.
- One of the barriers to building information modeling's widespread adoption is that, according to some businesses, it simply refers to 3D design. (7)

BUILDING INFORMATION MODELING IN SPAIN AND OTHER DEVELOPED NATIONS

The European Union's Directive 2014/24/UE has been put into effect in the Spanish construction sector. The Building Information Modeling (BIM) Directive, which will go into force in 2016, allows Member States to promote, utilize, and even require the use of BIM in building projects receiving EU funding. Spanish AEC experts use building information modeling to show that BIM technologies are now only deployed during the design phase of residential developments. This approach is seldom used in other kinds of projects or throughout the phases of building, operation, and maintenance. However, experts predict that it would take between three and five years BIM to be fully used in building projects (10). Building information modeling shown in Spain in Figure 4.

Building Information Modeling (BIM) is becoming more and more common in Spain, particularly in the construction and architectural sectors. Building information modeling (BIM) has recently been backed by the Spanish government in public projects, which has aided in raising awareness and promoting its use in the private sector. The use of BIM in Spain is encouraged by a number of professional associations, including the Spanish Association of Surveying and Mapping, the Spanish Association of Engineering and Architecture Firms, and the Spanish Association of Construction Companies. These groups educate clients and other stakeholders about the benefits of BIM and provide training and support to professionals who want to adopt it. Additionally, there are an increasing number of international companies like Autodesk and Trimble as well as Spanish companies like CYPE and Tekla who provide the BIM software. These companies provide a range of BIM tools and solutions, including as project management and collaboration platforms, design and modeling software, and more. A number of regulatory initiatives have been started by the Spanish government to promote the use of BIM in public projects. BIM, for instance, is now required for all public building projects in Spain as of 2018. In order to monitor the adoption of BIM across several sectors and to promote software tool standardization and interoperability, the government has also formed a BIM Commission. (23). In table number 1, you can see the definitions of advanced countries regarding the modeling of building information.

Country	Initiative
Australia	The Built Environment Industry Initiative Council published recommendations to establish requirements for fully collaborative BIM on Government building procurements by 1 July 2016, however no action was taken. New South Wales' Health Infrastructure has mandated BIM deliverables on all projects over \$30 million (9)
China	A BIM initiative is included in China's 2013 5-year plan, and a development of national guidelines has begun. (10)
Denmark	Denmark's government agencies implemented the Digital Construction program in 2007 which requires projects over

	5.5m Euros to use the IFC format and produce certain deliverables for facilities management (11)
Finland	The government required models to meet the IFC standard on all projects in 2007 and has outlined its objective to have “all-embracing, integrated model based operations in designing, building and property servicing and maintenance in a few years” (11)
Norway	The government agency responsible for construction projects, Statsbygg, in 2010 required that all properties use the IFC based BIM for the lifecycle whole lifecycle of the facility. (12)
Singapore	Singapore’s government is applying for a mandate for BIM by 2015, as well as providing incentives for “early pathfinders” (12). In addition to this, CORENET, a government development, is a fully funded resource provided by the government for automated code checking of models. (11)
South Korea	South Korea’s Public Procurement Service has made it compulsory for all projects over SK50m and for all public sector projects by 2016 (12)
United Kingdom	The UK Government Construction Strategy, published in 2011, set the requirement for the implementation of fully-collaborative BIM on all of its projects by 2016” (13).
USA	The General Services Administration has required mandatory BIM submission for governmental projects since 2008 (10)

Table 1: BIM Initiatives around the world

Building information modeling in prefabricated concrete parts

Precast concrete is often defined as concrete that is manufactured and treated in a factory setting before being delivered to the project site. Due to industrial manufacturing, this kind of concrete is made in a way that ensures good quality. Despite the fact that BIM is used in building projects, it is also seen necessary in the prefab business. BIM is a relatively new concept that initially has a narrow definition that only refers to the CAD model and information associated with it before expanding throughout the course of an organization's life cycle. Therefore, if BIM is properly implemented, it may modify the project participants' responsibilities and communication, as well as lower the project's cost and duration. (3) Constructing information modeling has many uses today, from designing and constructing structures to operating them and even destroying them. By digitally exhibiting the building's attributes, this technology assists the project management and stakeholders in making the best choice at every step. Modeling of building information all construction management tasks, which are based on contract papers, are reliant on the two types of maps and specifications, in that maps are used to define the scope of the work and technical specifications are used to determine its quality. In actuality, these two categories are used to set the performance assessment standards for contractors. We already know that the

execution plans of various design groups are generated independently but in collaboration with one another in the typical manner of construction management. On the one hand, plans and specifications are provided separately. Everyone can see the apparent drawbacks of this approach, and maybe the worst ones are the lack of cooperation, errors, and redoing work. In Figure 5, the design of precast concrete is done using the required design software.

Figure 5: Precast concrete design using software (23)

Advantages OF Precast concrete

- High speed construction
- lower costs
- high quality parts
- storage of parts
- ability to operate in adverse weather
- construction of temporary structures and reuse of parts;
- easier control of creep and shrinkage of prefabricated parts
- less manpower
- better planning and project management
- better use of pre-tensioning and post-tensioning techniques (14-1).

Disadvantages of precast concrete

- High initial investment is required
- Unique arrangements for transporting and implementing components need to be designed and considered
- Parts need to be adjusted and weigh a certain amount
- There are design and implementation constraints (14–15).

Construction information modeling technology in precast concrete

- Ability to analyze the structure
- Capability to review construction phases
- Possibility of precise planning of workshop equipment
- Scheduling schedule and sequence of manufacturing operations of prefabricated parts
- Estimation of the construction cost of the prefabricated structure
- Integration of information from subcontractors and material
- Coordination between systems (16-17-18)

Steps to use BIM in precast concrete

In general, there will be three main stages in the phased review of the building by BIM, which are:

Step 1) Before construction

Step 2) under construction

Step 3) After construction

It should be observed that the aforementioned stages are not clearly separated from one another; rather, they are all interconnected. Following these steps will help you arrive at design strategies that reduce the environmental effect of your building while considering its life cycle. Pre-construction activities include site selection, building design, and activities related to building design that take place prior to the establishment and use of materials. The sustainable design strategy considers the effects on the environment of structural design, building orientation, its impact on the surrounding landscape, and the materials utilized. A building's physical construction and usage are referred to as the "construction stage" of a building's life cycle. The sustainable design approach looks at how buildings are constructed and run in order to identify solutions to decrease the negative environmental consequences of resource usage. They also consider the long-term consequences of the surrounding environment on the health of the building's tenants. (19)

The post-construction phase begins as soon as the structure has served its purpose. At this point, the building materials will either be repurposed into new constructions or will be dumped back into nature as trash. A crucial aspect of the sustainable design approach is reducing construction waste by recycling and reusing buildings and construction materials. (19)

A building's physical construction and usage are referred to as the "construction stage" of a building's life cycle. In order to identify strategies to lessen the negative environmental consequences of resource use, the design, construction, and operation of buildings are evaluated. The long-term health consequences of the building's surroundings on its occupants are also taken into consideration. The post-construction phase begins as soon as the structure has served its purpose. At this

point, the building materials will either be repurposed into new constructions or will be dumped back into nature as trash. A crucial aspect of the sustainable design approach is reducing construction waste by recycling and reusing buildings and construction materials.

The five primary subgroups that make up the work process are: Utilizing BIM to divide up additional implementation phases

- First phase: before construction
- Second phase: construction
- The third phase: accurate and detailed design
- The fourth phase: preliminary design
- The fifth phase: planning

The effect of using BIM in precast concrete

In general, the following aspects may be taken into account when evaluating the impact of BIM on the technical parameters of concrete structures:

Weight: By incorporating the weight of the concrete component in the information data, the executive engineers may gain significantly. For instance, it will be able to select the kind and tonnage of the required crane by entering the part's weight and telling the installation engineer of it, guaranteeing safety during installation. The delivery of components also uses more conventional techniques and adequate equipment, which is crucial economically.

Dimensions: By knowing the part's dimensions and including them in the Bim data, it is possible to more precisely examine the part's location and the space that is available for its installation. Additionally, it is possible to choose the best equipment for transporting and installing the part while also avoiding implementation issues.

Fire resistance: As one of the primary considerations in the design and construction of concrete structures' fire resistance choice, ASTM E, prefabricated concrete panels composed of light grains, silica, carbonate, and light sand vary in their fire resistance and depend on the piece's thickness. In this standard, the amount of fire resistance lasting between one and four hours is considered. Understanding the prefabricated component's degree of fire resistance, which relies on the materials used and the thickness of the piece (for example, in parking lots or commercial areas with significant traffic), will help you pick the best place and circumstance for deploying it.

Implementation method: Implementation is one of the most critical and crucial phases in the building precast concrete components. It is feasible to describe the working environment, including the temperature, in BIM.

Part coding: The installation order of the pieces and the position of each part may be researched by entering the code and the number of the prefabricated part in BIM.

Connections: The right and principled installation of components may be achieved by using the right form of connection between prefabricated elements, such as beams, columns, slabs, foundations, etc.

Consumable components: One of the most significant and determining aspects in the creation of prefabricated parts is the consumption of components and their physical and chemical properties. The aforementioned details and attributes are equally applicable to Bim. (1)

Design: BIM allows for the entry of data pertaining to the design of prefabricated members, applicable rules, the amount of steel utilized in the component, etc. (1)

Figure 5: A summary of the impact of BIM on precast concrete parts (author)

Conclusion

Precast concrete structures can benefit from using the BIM method in many ways, such as speeding up project completion, improving workshop management, installing parts without any unintentional errors, properly coding parts and streamlining the installation process, producing precast concrete with high quality (due to the monitoring of consumables and the factory process of its manufacture), and better managing parts transportation without any potential problems. In light of the aforementioned benefits, it is advised that BIM technology be used in all prefabricated buildings, whether they are high-rise or multi-story, in order to speed up the construction process and improve accuracy and efficiency of implementation. To maximize accuracy in the process and avoid some from being overlooked, take into account the specifics and executive details of the

prefabricated concrete structures, including connections, plates, reinforcements, apertures, etc. It will be impossible to escape the finer points of employing the BIM approach. In addition to their complexity, prefabricated parts also have various production methods. As a result, the concrete mixes produced in various locations differ significantly from one another due to the various materials used there and the unique climatic conditions of each location. They are, in general, prefabricated concrete structures built with building information modeling technology can be built more accurately from the design stage to operation, avoid some unpleasant possibilities and events that could delay the project's construction, and reduce unnecessary costs.

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